

As on 29-1-2020, the following data collection and data entry procedures are recommended to add records in Product Image table in the Global Knowledge Base System.

Steps recommended for collecting crop images:

1. Use Google Advanced Image Search engine to find the image of the crop.
2. Use the scientific name of the crop to ensure the right crop is taken.

Steps for data entry:

1. Prior to data entry, one should know the following:
 - **'Product Image'** is the table to record the image of the derived product for specific crop.
 - Procedures of data entry into the database (how to enter the data into the table); user will be trained for the data entry before entering data.
2. **IMPORTANT:** Prior to data entry, one has to ensure there is **NO** redundant data in previous record which has the same data to be created in the database.
3. There are 4 fields to be entered, **three** of them are meant to be compulsory for every record.

3.1 Derived Product (Auto-generated)

- This is referring to the name of the derived product which previously entered in "Derived Product" table.

3.2 Image (Compulsory)

- This field is to link the product image to the stored image in 'Image' table. See how to store image in 'Image' table in SOP – Collecting Images (<https://1drv.ms/w/s!AtJcPbYdz7XHeiFZTcRwytDY9ww?e=mFj6tR>)
- Please take note that the image **MUST** to be stored into the 'Image' table first before creating this record.

3.3 Notes

- This field is to store the extra information related to the product of the specific crop itself.

3.4 Metadata ID (Compulsory)

- This field is to link the record to the metadata of derived product.
- One **MUST** create a Metadata record in 'Metadata' table before entering Metadata ID.